

THE ROLE OF NURSES IN DISPENSARY MONITORING OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GASTRITIS IN POLYCLINIC SETTINGS

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ABSTRACT

Chronic gastritis is one of the most widespread diseases worldwide and has a significant impact on public health. It occurs in various population groups and, if not properly controlled, may lead to serious complications. Regular monitoring of patients in polyclinic settings helps reduce complications and improve the quality of life of patients. The effectiveness of dispensary monitoring depends not only on physicians but also significantly on nurses.

Introduction: Chronic gastritis is one of the most widespread diseases worldwide and has a significant impact on public health. It occurs in various population groups and, if not properly controlled, may lead to serious complications. Regular monitoring of patients in polyclinic settings helps reduce complications and improve the quality of life of patients. The effectiveness of dispensary monitoring depends not only on physicians but also significantly on nurses.

Objectives. To determine the role and effectiveness of nurses in organizing dispensary monitoring of patients with chronic gastritis in polyclinic settings.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted in 2025–2026 at the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center and Peshku District Medical Association. A total of 120 patients aged 20–60 years with chronic gastritis were included in the study. All patients were under regular outpatient (dispensary) monitoring. Data were collected from outpatient medical records and through specially designed questionnaires. Patients' lifestyle, dietary habits, and medication adherence were analyzed.

Result: "A total of 120 patients diagnosed with chronic gastritis participated in the study."

Women accounted for 60%

-Men accounted for 40%

Frequency of medical check-ups:

-Once every 3 months – 10%

-Once every 6 months – 35.8%

-Once a year – 54.2%

Reasons for not attending preventive check-ups:

-Low quality of preventive services – 54%

-Long waiting times in polyclinics – 38%

-Work-related busyness – 8%

Conclusion: The findings indicate that the majority of patients with chronic gastritis are women. Most patients undergo medical examinations once a year, which highlights the need to improve the effectiveness of dispensary monitoring. The main reasons for non-attendance at preventive check-ups are the low quality of services and long waiting times in polyclinics. Improving the quality of preventive care and reducing waiting times are essential measures for enhancing the healthcare system

References:

- 1.Mamatqulov, S. (2020). Dispensary monitoring of patients in gastroenterology. Journal of Medicine and Health, 5(2), 34–40.
- 2.Baratova M., Makhmudova M. Predictors of sudden death in patients with arterial hypertension //InterConf.-2020. – 2020. № 1(37). P. 695-697
- 3.Rakhimova, D., & Akbarov, F. (2019). Preventive examinations in polyclinics and ways to increase patient participation. Tashkent: Medpress.
- 4.Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2022). Guidelines for monitoring chronic gastritis and other gastrointestinal diseases in polyclinics. Tashkent.

